

Integrated Modular Middle-Layer for Gemini Robotics-ER with One-Shot Planning for Shelf Arrangement

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Abstract

Vision-Language-Action (VLA) models have emerged as promising solutions for robotic manipulation by enabling robots to interpret natural language instructions and generate action sequences. Recently, many state-of-the-art general VLA frameworks have been developed as dual-architecture systems that separate a high-level reasoning module from a low-level action module, enabling a "think-before-acting" paradigm for multi-step manipulation.

Gemini Robotics 1.5 [1] exemplifies this design through an agentic system that couples an embodied reasoning model, Gemini Robotics-ER 1.5 (a vision-language model, VLM), with an action model (VLA). In this closed-loop stack, Gemini Robotics-ER 1.5 serves as the orchestrator that interprets user instructions and perceptual inputs, reasons about the physical scene, and decomposes long-horizon objectives into ordered sub-tasks. The VLA component then translates these sub-tasks into low-level robot actions for execution. However, practical use of Gemini Robotics-ER 1.5 via APIs can be constrained by token and request limits, and access to the complete action model can be restricted, which complicates full end-to-end reproduction in public settings.

Additionally, a dual-module design is adopted in Bi-VLA for bimanual dexterous manipulation [2]. Bi-VLA transforms a user request (voice) and a scene image into structured intermediate outputs, including a JSON representation of task-relevant entities (e.g., item lists and 2D pixel locations). An action module then uses this JSON representation to generate an ordered sequence of action API calls for bimanual execution. Although Bi-VLA is demonstrated to support instruction understanding, scene-aware perception, and coordinated bimanual execution, it is evaluated in a task-specific household cooking setting (e.g., salad preparation), focusing on a limited set of manipulation operations such as picking, placing, and cutting ingredients.

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Figure 1: (a) System diagram of vanilla Gemini Robotics-ER 1.5 without correction layer, illustrating the one-shot planning architecture where multimodal prompts (text instruction: and RGB camera image) are processed through Gemini’s VLM for high-level planning, generating a JSON task plan that executes in a closed-loop with the Gazebo simulation environment through low-level MoveIt2 control. Initial configuration showing objects randomly distributed on the workspace table with an empty two-compartment shelf. Resulting arrangement after vanilla Gemini execution, exhibiting significant spatial estimation errors with objects placed at incorrect positions and orientations, demonstrating the limitations of one-shot planning without correction layers. (b) IMMC-OSP integrated modular middle-layer achieving precision manipulation. System diagram with integrated correction layer, incorporating FoundationPose for 6D pose estimation and MaxRects-BL for collision-free placement planning. Initial configuration with objects on the workspace table and empty shelf. Resulting arrangement after full-system correction, achieving precise and collision-free object placement with 100% task success rate. (c) Comprehensive error metrics comparing Gemini baseline with IMMC-OSP corrections across position, yaw, and size dimensions.

Motivated by these dual-system designs, this paper presents a pipeline that leverages Gemini Robotics-ER 1.5 to produce a structured action plan in JSON format from a single query consisting of an image and a text prompt, referred to as one-shot planning. Our developed action model subsequently retrieves the JSON plan and executes the corresponding robot actions. One-shot planning is designed to avoid API usage limitations by eliminating iterative API interactions; however, this design can reduce spatial accuracy because object localization, grasp positions, and placement parameters cannot be refined through repeated perception updates. To address this limitation, we introduce an integrated modular middle layer that refines the one-shot JSON plan into high-precision grasping and placement specifications.

Experimental analysis in Gazebo simulation with dual-arm UR5e robots performing a shelf-arrangement task—placing eatable and uneatable boxes onto the left and right shelves, respectively—shows that, although Gemini Robotics-ER 1.5 (without correction layer) achieves 100% semantic classification accuracy (i.e. correctly classifying boxes as eatable or uneatable), its spatial estimation capabilities are insufficient for precision manipulation, with position errors averaging 19.7 cm, yaw errors of 46.2°, and size errors of 27.6 mm, far exceeding the sub-centimeter tolerances required for reliable grasping and placement (Figure 1a). Noted that the clear prompt is explicitly provided (see Figure 1a-II), whereas the unclear prompt is formulated based on the performance of Gemini Robotics-ER 1.5 and is not the focus of this study.

To overcome this limitation, we propose the Integrated Modular Middle-layer for Corrective One-Shot Planning (IMMC-OSP), a correction layer that refines the one-shot JSON plan into high-precision grasping and placement specifications for shelf arrangement tasks (Figure 1b). The system integrates two complementary correction modules in a sequential pipeline that systematically addresses Gemini’s spatial limitations: (1) FoundationPose for 6D pose estimation [3], which learns both shape and appearance representations of objects to generate multiple pose hypotheses—essential for resolving ambiguities in symmetrical objects and partially occluded scenes—then employs a scoring and refinement mechanism to select the optimal pose estimate, providing accurate 3D position, orientation (yaw), and object dimensions; and (2) MaxRects-BL bin packing algorithm [4] for deterministic collision-free shelf placement computation, which takes the corrected object dimensions from FoundationPose to recalculate optimal placement positions, ensuring robust spatial arrangement without collisions.

The experimental result demonstrates that IMMC-OSP transforms Gemini’s spatial estimates from unusable to fully operational. Although vanilla Gemini Robotics-ER 1.5 is unable to complete the task due to robot-shelf collisions, the full-correction implementation achieves a task success rate of 100% across all test conditions. The correction layer reduces position error by 97.8% (from 19.7 cm to 3.3 mm), yaw error by 99.3% (from 44.8° to 0.3°), and size error by 96.6% (from 31.8 mm to 1.08 mm), as shown in Figure 1c.

Taken together, these results indicate that combining VLM-driven semantic reasoning with geometry-based corrective perception provides the spatial precision required for reliable one-shot VLA execution in precision manipulation tasks. By introducing IMMC-OSP as an intermediate correction layer, this work addresses the fundamental mismatch between the semantic strengths and spatial limitations inherent in current VLM-based planning systems. The modular architecture enables each component to operate within its domain of expertise: Gemini Robotics-ER 1.5 provides robust high-level task understanding and object classification, while FoundationPose delivers sub-centimeter pose accuracy and MaxRects-BL ensures collision-free placement computation. This decomposition not only resolves

the immediate spatial accuracy problem but also circumvents API constraints by eliminating the need for iterative refinement queries, preserving the efficiency of one-shot planning while achieving the geometric precision necessary for real-world deployment. However, this study is limited to rigid objects. In future work, we will extend the framework to a broader range of objects and deploy IMMC-OSP on a physical dual-arm robot to validate its performance in real-world scenarios.

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